

Optimized method of coating the microwave ablation probe for surgical application

John Fiallos^{1,2}, Haniyeh Ghavidel, Joe Bolanos^{1,2}, Kevin Morris^{1,2}, Marco Amaya^{1,2}, Susanne Strand^{1,2}, Maryori Placencio³, Vicky Yamamoto^{1,2}, Robert Hariri⁴, Jason Cormier^{1,5}, Saleem Abdulrauf⁶, Babak Kateb^{1,2}

Society for Brain Mapping and Therapeutics¹, Brain Mapping Foundation², Ministry of Public Health of Ecuador³, Celularity Corporation⁴, Acadiana Neurosurgery⁵, Saint Louis University⁶

ABSTRACT

Thermal ablation procedures use heat to remove tissue inducing cellular death via coagulation necrosis. The current ablation procedure includes radiofrequency ablation (RFA) and microwave ablation (MWA). The major limitation of all heat-based thermal ablation devices is the lack of predictability of the ablation zone size and shape. Our development presents an optimized microwave ablation through the isolation of the probe tip and the anode with Parylene C. With this coated probe, there is no direct contact or through fluids between the microwave to the brain tissue, showing a more complete, secure and uniform ablation zone than achieved by conventional electrical insulation.

BACKGROUND

The thermal ablative procedures raise the tumor temperature (50⁰ C to 80⁰ C), which modifies tumor cell morphology and function, causing coagulative necrosis and tumor cell death when the temperature exceed 50⁰ C. The RFA uses radiofrequency waves directly to the tumor to destroy tumor cells with heat 140⁰ F. Tissue boiling and charring act as electrical insulators and limit the effect of RFA through increased impedance, RFA is also partially limited by the heat-sink effect. Consequently, the shape and size of the ablation zone may be unpredictable and efficacy of RFA may be restricted as multiple sessions are necessary for complete tumor eradication.¹ MWA is a recent development in the field of tumor ablation, uses electromagnetic (EM) waves to create a microwave near-field with direct friction and heat, thus inducing cellular death via coagulation necrosis.²

The frequency of 2.4 GHz is the one most commonly employed, whereas the frequency of 915 MHz can facilitate deeper penetration. MWA systems create a large active heating zone, thus permitting more uniform

necrosis in the target lesion with no skin burns. However, the major limitation of all heat-based thermal ablation devices is the lack of predictability of the ablation zone size and shape.³ In addition, the shape of the EM field, which is elliptical with conventional MWA systems, cannot be modified according to the presence of adjacent vessels (Fig. 1). These limitation must be overcome to achieve the desired outcomes.³

FIG. 1: The shape of the ablation zone of RFA system, conventional MWA system. A) RFA has a heat-sink effect. Flow of blood through vessels cools the surrounding tissue, preventing complete ablation in proximity to vessels and distorting the passive ablation zone. B) The shape of the electromagnetic field induced by a conventional MWA system is affected less by the adjacent vessels, but the field has an elliptical shape.

METHODS

The optimized microwave ablation probe tip isolation is achieved if the probe tip and anode is coated with Parylene C. With this coated there is no contact directly or through fluids between the microwave to the brain tissue. The Parylene C coating is approximately 2-3 microns and is not prone to cracking or electrical leakage but similarly does not interfere with or alter the electromagnetic transmission of energy. The coating cycle begins with vaporization of the powdered raw material and (dimer) at 1500C., creating a dimer gas. The problem to solve is to have biocompatible seal over the probe materials that is adequately robust to remain electrically and mechanically uncompromised throughout its life up to and including the surgical procedure. At the same time the material needs to provide minimal interruption of the microwave energy field that provides the thermal treatment of the tissue.

RESULTS

While such neurological microwave ablation probes are conventionally insulated with one or more layers of insulation to prevent direct electrical connection of the microwave current to tissue. It is the object of this invention to provides electrical isolation of the probe tip and anode from the tissue, in order to extent more complete and more secure than achieved by conventional electrical insulation.

CONCLUSIONS

We present a new microwave ablation procedure using Parylene C coating on the probe tip and anode. Further validation is recommended on a larger technological clinical trials. This invention shows an overcome of the limitations of the conventional microwave ablation, giving to the surgeon better outcomes to improve the ablation of tumors.

REFERENCES

- 1.Poulou, L. S., Botsa, E., Thanou, I., Ziakas, P. D., & Thanos, L. (2015). Percutaneous microwave ablation vs radiofrequency ablation in the treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma. *World journal of hepatology*, 7(8), 1054-1063. <https://doi.org/10.4254/wjh.v7.i8.1054>
- 2.Brace C. L. (2010). Microwave tissue ablation: biophysics, technology, and applications. *Critical reviews in biomedical engineering*, 38(1), 65-78. <https://doi.org/10.1615/critrevbiomedeng.v38.i1.60>
- 3.Imajo, K., Ogawa, Y., Yoneda, M. et al. A review of conventional and newer generation microwave ablation systems for hepatocellular carcinoma. *J Med Ultrasonics* (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10396-019-00997-5>.

Acknowledgements: This research is made possible by the generous contributions of Brain Mapping Foundation.